

A COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF ANALYTICAL, INTEGRAL AND NUMERICAL APPROACHES FOR INDUCTANCE CALCULATION IN FERROMAGNETIC MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Accurate inductance calculation is a fundamental requirement in the design of magnetic components employing ferromagnetic cores. In classical magnetic circuit theory, inductance is commonly estimated using an average magnetic path length together with lumped-parameter assumptions on permeability and magnetic field distribution. While this approach provides analytical simplicity, it implicitly assumes a uniform magnetic field intensity along the magnetic circuit. In practical magnetic structures, particularly air-gapped ferromagnetic cores, this assumption is often violated due to spatial variations of the magnetic field, nonlinear material characteristics, and flux fringing effects at the air gap boundaries.

In air-gapped magnetic circuits, a dominant portion of the magnetomotive force is concentrated across the air gap, resulting in a nonuniform magnetic field distribution along the magnetic path. The presence of an air gap significantly alters the effective magnetic reluctance and introduces fringing flux effects that cannot be accurately represented using a single average magnetic path length parameter. Furthermore, the nonlinear B–H characteristics of ferromagnetic materials cause the effective permeability to vary with the operating point, which directly affects inductance values under different excitation conditions.

Integral-based formulations provide an alternative analytical framework by expressing the magnetomotive force as a line integral of the magnetic field intensity along the flux path, allowing spatial field variations to be incorporated into inductance calculations. In this study, inductance calculation approaches based on average magnetic path length approximations, integral formulations, and numerical field solutions obtained using the finite element method (FEM) are comparatively evaluated for air-gapped ferromagnetic cores. Magnetostatic FEM enables detailed resolution of magnetic flux density distribution and fringing effects that are difficult to capture using simplified magnetic circuit models. The comparative evaluation indicates that the average magnetic path length

assumption may introduce noticeable deviations in air-gapped configurations, whereas integral formulations and FEM-based analyses provide more consistent representations of magnetic field distribution and inductance behavior. The study aims to support the selection of appropriate inductance calculation techniques for practical magnetic component design.

Keywords: Inductance Calculation, Ferromagnetic Core, Magnetic Circuit, Finite Element Method

1) INTRODUCTION

The design of magnetic components such as inductors and transformers requires accurate determination of inductance values under various operating conditions. In power electronic applications, inductors with ferromagnetic cores are widely used for energy storage, filtering, and current shaping purposes. The inductance of these components directly influences their electrical performance, dynamic response, and overall system efficiency. Traditional magnetic circuit theory provides a convenient analytical framework by treating the magnetic system as an equivalent circuit with magnetomotive force sources and magnetic reluctances (Karapetoff, 1911; MIT Department of Electrical Engineering, 1943). This lumped-parameter approach remains popular in engineering practice due to its computational simplicity and ease of implementation.

The classical magnetic circuit method typically assumes that magnetic flux is uniformly distributed along an average magnetic path length through the core material. For closed-core configurations, where the magnetic path is entirely contained within high-permeability ferromagnetic material, this assumption provides reasonable accuracy. However, when an air gap is introduced into the magnetic circuit, the validity of the uniform flux distribution assumption becomes questionable. Air gaps are deliberately incorporated in many inductor designs to prevent core saturation, increase energy storage capability, and linearize the inductance characteristic (Hurley and Wölfle, 2013). The presence of an air gap significantly increases the total reluctance of the magnetic circuit because the permeability of air is approximately three orders of magnitude lower than that of common ferromagnetic materials. As a result, a large portion of the magnetomotive force is consumed across the air gap region, leading to a concentrated magnetic field intensity in that area and non-uniform field distribution along the magnetic path.

A well-known limitation of the simple magnetic circuit approach in air-gapped structures is its inability to properly account for fringing flux. (Roshen, 2007). Near the air gap boundaries, magnetic flux tends to spread outward into the surrounding air rather than remaining confined to the core cross-section. This fringing phenomenon occurs because the high reluctance of the gap causes flux lines to seek alternative paths with lower reluctance. The fringing effect increases the effective cross-sectional area through which flux passes, thereby reducing the actual reluctance of the air gap compared to the theoretical value calculated assuming uniform flux confinement (Balakrishnan et al., 1997). Several empirical correction factors have been proposed to approximately compensate for fringing effects

(McLyman, 2011; Kazimierczuk, 2009). However, these correction factors are derived from specific geometric configurations and may not accurately represent field distributions in structures that deviate from the idealized cases.

Another important consideration in inductance calculation is the nonlinear magnetic behavior of ferromagnetic materials. The relationship between magnetic flux density and magnetic field intensity in ferromagnetic cores is inherently nonlinear and exhibits hysteresis. The effective permeability varies significantly with the operating point and decreases as the core approaches magnetic saturation (Cullity and Graham, 2009). In the linear region of operation, the relative permeability of ferromagnetic materials can reach several thousand, whereas near saturation it approaches unity. This nonlinearity implies that the inductance of a ferromagnetic-core inductor is not constant but depends on the excitation level. Conventional magnetic circuit analysis often assumes a constant effective permeability value, which may be acceptable for small-signal or linear-region operation but can introduce considerable errors when the core operates near saturation or under large-signal excitation (Erickson and Maksimovic, 2001).

Alternative analytical formulations have been developed to improve upon the basic magnetic circuit approach. One such method involves expressing the magnetomotive force as a line integral of the magnetic field intensity along the actual flux path. This integral formulation allows spatial variations in field intensity to be explicitly incorporated, rather than being averaged into a single path length parameter. By integrating field intensity over different regions of the magnetic circuit—including sections with different permeabilities and varying field concentrations—a more accurate representation of the total magnetomotive force can be obtained. This approach can sometimes approximate the result to the actual inductance, depending on the geometry of the model. However, in the case of a C-type core, due to the regular geometry, the integral is reduced, returning to the classical method formulas.

Numerical field solution methods, particularly the finite element method (FEM), have become standard tools for analyzing complex magnetic field problems. The finite element method discretizes the solution domain into a mesh of elements and solves Maxwell's equations subject to appropriate boundary conditions and material properties (Jin, 2002; Alisoy, 1996). FEM provides detailed spatial resolution of magnetic flux density and field intensity distributions throughout the entire problem domain, including the core, air gap, and surrounding regions. This capability enables accurate modeling of phenomena such as flux fringing, leakage flux, and nonlinear material characteristics that are difficult to capture using simplified circuit models (Bastos and Sadowski, 2003). Recent studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of FEM-based approaches for inductance calculation in various configurations, with particular attention to fringing effects and distributed air gaps (Stenglein and Albach, 2017; Jez, 2017). Similar finite element optimization methods have been successfully applied to magnetic coupler design and other magnetic component applications (Arslan et al., 2023).

Despite the accuracy advantages offered by numerical methods, analytical and semi-analytical approaches remain valuable for preliminary design, parametric studies, and rapid design iterations. Analytical methods provide closed-form or semi-closed-form expressions that offer direct insight into the relationships between design parameters and performance characteristics. In contrast, while numerical methods provide high accuracy, they typically require significant computational effort and may not readily reveal the underlying physical relationships governing the design (Matsch, 1964). Therefore, understanding the relative accuracy and applicability of different calculation methods is important for effective design practice.

The objective of the present study is to compare three distinct approaches for calculating inductance in air-gapped ferromagnetic core configurations: the classical average magnetic path length method, an integral-based analytical formulation, and numerical analysis using the finite element method. The study focuses on a representative air-gapped core geometry where effects such as flux fringing, reluctance distribution, and field non-uniformity are expected to be significant. By comparing inductance values and examining the underlying assumptions of each method, the study aims to provide practical guidance on selecting appropriate calculation techniques for magnetic component design.

2) MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1) Core Geometry and Material Properties

The study is based on an air-gapped C-type ferromagnetic core, as illustrated in Figure 1. A discrete air gap is positioned on the upper yoke to regulate magnetic reluctance and prevent core saturation. While the classical analytical method assumes an initial relative permeability $\mu_r = 2000$ to provide a baseline calculation, the study further investigates the nonlinear magnetic behavior of the Pure Iron core. In practical scenarios, the effective permeability is not constant but varies according to the operating point on the B–H curve. Detailed geometric dimensions and excitation parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. Air Gapped C Type Ferromagnetic Core

Table 1. Parameters of the Modeled Magnetic Circuit

Parameter	Value	Unit	Symbol
Core Material	Pure Iron	-	-
Initial Relative Permeability	2000	-	μ_r
Air Gap Length	1×10^{-3}	m	l_g
Number of Turns	100	-	N
Excitation Current	1.0	A	I
Wire Gauge	18	AWG	-
Core Cross-Section	6×10^{-4}	m^2	A_c
Mean Path Length	0,319	m	l_c

2.2) Classical Magnetic Circuit Method

The classical magnetic circuit analysis models reluctances in series, assuming a uniform distribution of flux.

$$\mathcal{R}_c = l_c / (\mu_0 \mu_r A_c) \quad (1)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_g = l_g / (\mu_0 A_c) \quad (2)$$

where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m is the permeability of free space. The total reluctance is

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{R}_c + \mathcal{R}_g \quad (3)$$

and the inductance;

$$L_{\text{classical}} = N^2 / \mathcal{R}_{\text{total}} = N^2 \mu_0 A_c / (l_c/\mu_r + l_g) \quad (4)$$

Substituting the parameters from Table 1 into Eqs. (1)–(4);

$$\mathcal{R}_c = 0.319 / (4\pi \times 10^{-7} \times 2000 \times 600 \times 10^{-6}) \approx 2.12 \times 10^5 \text{ A/Wb} \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_g = 0.001 / (4\pi \times 10^{-7} \times 600 \times 10^{-6}) \approx 1.326 \times 10^6 \text{ A/Wb} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_{\text{total}} = 2.12 \times 10^5 + 1.326 \times 10^6 \approx 1.538 \times 10^6 \text{ A/Wb} \quad (7)$$

$$L_{\text{classical}} = (100)^2 / (1.538 \times 10^6) \approx \mathbf{6.5 \text{ mH}} \quad (8)$$

2.3) Integral-Based Formulation

The integral approach expresses the magnetomotive force as a line integral of magnetic field intensity along the flux path, according to Ampère's law:

$$NI = \oint \mathbf{H} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \int_{\text{core}} H_c \, dl + \int_{\text{gap}} H_g \, dl \quad (9)$$

In the core region, $H_c = B_c / (\mu_0 \mu_r)$, and in the gap, $H_g = B_g / \mu_0$. Assuming flux continuity ($\Phi = BA_c$) and integrating over each region yields:

$$NI = \Phi [l_c / (\mu_0 \mu_r A_c) + l_g / (\mu_0 A_c)] \quad (10)$$

If the Eq.(10) is arranged;

$$L_{\text{integral}} = N^2 / \mathcal{R}_{\text{total}} \quad (11)$$

It is seen that Eq.(10) is equivalent to Eq.(4), so the inductance found by integration is also **6.5 mH**.

2.4) Finite Element Method

The FEM analysis solves the magnetostatic field equations numerically using the magnetic vector potential formulation. The governing equation in two dimensions is;

$$\nabla \cdot (\nu \nabla A_z) = -J_z \quad (12)$$

where $\nu = 1/\mu$ is the reluctivity, A_z is the z-component of the vector potential, and J_z is the current density in the winding. The magnetic flux density is obtained from $B = \nabla \times A$. For nonlinear materials, the reluctivity is a function of flux density magnitude, and the B–H characteristic is represented using piecewise linear interpolation or analytical functions (Bastos and Sadowski, 2003).

The solution domain includes the core, air gap, winding region, and surrounding air. A Dirichlet boundary condition ($A_z = 0$) is applied at the outer boundary. The domain is discretized into triangular elements with mesh refinement at the air gap boundaries to resolve fringing effects. The finite element equations are assembled using the Galerkin method and solved iteratively for nonlinear materials. After obtaining the field solution, the total flux linking the winding is calculated by integrating flux density over a cross-sectional surface.

3) RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Unlike the analytical calculations in Section 2, which assumed a constant relative $\mu_r = 2000$ permeability, the Finite Element Analysis incorporates the actual nonlinear magnetic characteristics of the core material. The B–H curve of the Pure Iron used in the simulation is presented in Figure 3. Defining this nonlinear relationship is crucial for accurately capturing saturation effects and the variation of permeability across the core.

Figure 3. B-H Curve Of Pure Iron Used in FEMM Simulation

Based on this material definition, the magnetostatic solution was computed at the nominal current ($I = 1A$). The resulting magnetic flux density distribution is illustrated in Figure 4. The color map indicates the magnitude of flux density throughout the C-core geometry. As observed, the flux is well-confined within the core, but the distribution is not perfectly uniform due to the geometric corners and the air gap.

Figure 4. Distribution Of Magnetic Flux Density Magnitude Across The C-Core Reactor At Nominal Current

Following the finite element solution shown in Figure 4, the total magnetic energy stored in the system domain was computed. The simulation yielded a total magnetic energy of **0.00445141 Joules** at the nominal current of **1 A**. Consequently, the inductance is calculated directly from the energy definition as:

$$L_{FEMM} = \frac{2W}{I^2} \quad (13)$$

From FEMM simulation;

$$L_{FEMM} = \frac{2 \times 0.00445141}{1^2} \approx 8.9\text{mH} \quad (14)$$

This value represents the true inductance of the reactor, accounting for both the saturation of the core and the fringing flux distributed around the air gap.

Table 2. Comparison of Inductance Calculation Results

Method	Model Assumption	Inductance (L)
Classical	Linear ($\mu_r = 2000$), No Fringing	6.5mH
Integral	Linear ($\mu_r = 2000$), No Fringing	6.5mH
Finite Elements Method (FEMM Simulation)	Nonlinear (B-H Curve), Fringing	8.9mH

As seen in Table 2, the analytical methods provide a baseline inductance of **6.5 mH**. However, the FEMM simulation yields a significantly higher inductance of **8.9 mH**. This approximately 37% difference is primarily attributed to the **fringing flux** around the air gap, which effectively increases the cross-sectional area of the magnetic path, thereby reducing the total reluctance. Additionally, the inclusion of the **nonlinear B–H curve** in FEMM captures the true permeability variations in the core, providing a more realistic representation compared to the constant permeability model.

CONCLUSION

This study presented a comparative analysis of inductance calculation methods for an air-gapped ferromagnetic reactor, highlighting the limitations of classical magnetic circuit theory against the precision of the Finite Element Method (FEM). While the classical and integral-based analytical formulations converged to a baseline inductance of 6.5 mH under linear assumptions, the energy-based numerical analysis revealed a significantly higher actual inductance of 8.9 mH. The reason why the same inductance value is found in both classical and integral-based approaches is due to the geometry of the core, which simplifies the integral to the classical formula.

The observed 37% discrepancy demonstrates that standard reluctance network models, which neglect fringing fluxes and assume uniform flux distribution, are insufficient for the accurate modeling of air-gapped cores. The results confirm that fringing fields around the air gap effectively increase the cross-sectional area of the magnetic path, drastically reducing the total reluctance compared to theoretical geometric predictions. Furthermore, the inclusion of the nonlinear B–H characteristics of Pure Iron in the FEM simulation captured local permeability variations that linear models fail to predict.

For power electronics designers, this deviation is critical. Relying solely on analytical formulas for component sizing can lead to substantial design errors, such as incorrect corner frequencies in LC filters or unexpected core saturation under load. Consequently, this work concludes that while analytical methods are suitable for initial approximation, numerical modeling or advanced analytical corrections accounting for fringing energy are indispensable for the final design verification of high-performance magnetic components.

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